

THE LIFE OF ALFRED LORD TENNYSON AND HIS STYLE OF WRITING

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Annotation: This article discusses the life of Alfred Tennyson and his unique style of poetry, as well as the exposition of his poems and their contribution to literary analysis and literature.

Keywords: writer, Chiefly Lyrical, poetic quality, Epic poetry, genius, medieval, Poet Laureate. Alfred Tennyson, 1st Baron Tennyson FRS (6 August 1809 – 6 October 1892) was an English poet. He was Poet Laureate for most of Queen Victoria's reign. In 1829, Tennyson was awarded the Chancellor's Gold Medal at Cambridge for one of his first works, *Timbuktu*. He published his first solo collection of poems in 1830, *Poems, Chiefly Lyrical*. This volume includes some of Tennyson's most famous poems, *Claribel* and *Mariana*. Although described by some critics as overly sentimental, his poems soon became popular and brought Tennyson to the attention of prominent writers of the day, including Samuel Taylor Coleridge. Tennyson's early poetry greatly influenced the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood with its medieval and powerful visual imagery.

The development of Tennyson's genius, methods, aims, and capacity of achievement in poetry can be studied with singular precision and fulness in the history of the poems included in the present volume. In 1842 he published the two volumes which gave him, by almost general consent, the first place among the poets of his time, for, though Wordsworth was alive, Wordsworth's best work had long been done. These two volumes contained poems that had appeared before, some in 1830 and some in 1832, and some which were then given to the world for the first time, so that they represent work belonging to three eras in the poet's life, poems written before he had completed his twenty-second year and belonging for the most part to his boyhood, poems written in his early manhood, and poems written between his thirty-first and thirty-fourth year. The poems published in 1830 had the following title page: "Poems, Chiefly Lyrical, by Alfred Tennyson. London: Effingham Wilson, Royal Exchange, 1830". They are fifty-six in number and the titles are: --Sonnet I. Sonnet II. *Mariana* in the South.

Tennyson's genius was slow in maturing. The poems contributed by him to the volume of 1827, 'Poems by Two Brothers', are not without some slight promise, but are very far from indicating extraordinary powers. A great advance is discernible in 'Timbuctoo', but that Matthew Arnold should have discovered in it the germ of Tennyson's future powers is probably to be attributed to the youth of the critic. Tennyson was in his twenty-second year when the 'Poems Chiefly Lyrical' appeared, and what strikes us in these poems is certainly not what Arthur Hallam saw in them: much rather what Coleridge and Wilson discerned in them. They are the poems of a fragile and somewhat morbid young man in whose temper we seem to see a touch of Hamlet, a touch of Romeo, and, more healthily, a touch of Mercutio. Their most promising characteristic is the versatility displayed.

Thus we find 'Mariana' side by side with the 'Supposed Confessions', the 'Ode to Memory' with Greek[oi rheontes]', 'The Ballad of Oriana' with 'The Dying Swan', 'Recollections of The Arabian Nights' with 'The Poet'. Their worst fault is affectation. Perhaps the utmost that can

be said for them is that they display a fine but somewhat thin vein of original genius, after deducing what they owe to Coleridge, Keats, and to other poets. This is seen in the magical touches of description, in the exquisite felicity of expression and rhythm which frequently mark them, in the pathos and power of such a poem as 'Oriana', in the pathos and charm of such poems as 'Mariana' and 'A Dirge', in the rich and almost gorgeous fancy displayed in 'The Recollections'.

The poems of 1833 are much more ambitious and strike deeper notes. Here comes in for the first time that Greek[spondai_otaes'], that high seriousness which is one of Tennyson's chief characteristics--we see it in 'The Palace of Art', in 'none' and in the verses 'To J. S.' But in intrinsic merit the poems were no advance on their predecessors, for the execution was not equal to the design. The best, such as 'none', 'A Dream of Fair Women', 'The Palace of Art', and 'The Lady of Shalott'--I am speaking of course of these poems in their first form--were full of extraordinary blemishes. The volume was degraded by pieces which were very unworthy of him, such as 'O Darling Room' and the verses 'To Christopher North', and affectations of the worst kind deformed many, nay, perhaps the majority of the poems. But the capital defect lay in the workmanship. The diction is often languid and slipshod, sometimes quaintly affected, and we can never go far without encountering lines, stanzas, a whole poems which cry aloud for the file. The power and charm of Tennyson's poetry, even at its ripest, depend very largely, often mainly, on expression, and the couplet which he envied Browning,

The little more, and how much it is,
The little less, and what worlds away

is strangely applicable to his own art. On a single word, on a subtle collocation, on a slight touch depend often his finest effects: "the little less" reduces him to mediocrity, "the little more" and he is with the masters. To no poetry would the application of Goethe's test be, as a rule, more fatal--that the real poetic quality in poetry is that which remains when it has been translated literally into prose.

In surveying these poems two things must strike everyone--their very wide range and their very fragmentary character. There is scarcely any side of life on which they do not touch, scarcely any phase of passion and emotion to which they do not give exquisite expression. Take the love poems: compare 'Fatima' with 'Isabel', 'The Miller's Daughter' with 'Locksley Hall', 'The Gardener's Daughter' with 'Madeline', or 'Mariana' with Cleopatra in the 'Dream of Fair Women'. When did love find purer and nobler expressions than in 'Love and Duty?' When has sorrow found utterance more perfect than in the verses 'To J. S.', or the passion for the past than in 'Break, Break, Break', or revenge and jealousy than in 'The Sisters?' In 'The Two Voices', 'The Palace of Art', and 'The Vision of Sin' we are in another sphere. They are appeals to the soul of man on subjects of momentous concern to him. And each is a masterpiece. What is proper to philosophy and what is proper to poetry have never perhaps been so happily blended. They have all the sensuous charm of Keats, but the prose of Hume could not have presented the truths which they are designed to convey with more lucidity and precision. In that superb fragment the 'Morte d'Arthur' we have many of the noblest attributes of Epic poetry. 'none' is the perfection of the classical idyll, 'The Gardener's Daughter', and the idylls that follow it of the romantic. 'Sir Galahad' and 'St. Agnes' is in the vein of Keats and Coleridge, but Keats and Coleridge have produced nothing more exquisite and nothing so ethereal. 'The Lotos* Eaters' is perhaps the most purely delicious poem ever written, the 'ne plus ultra' of

sensuous loveliness, and yet the poet who gave us that has given us also the political poems, poems as trenchant and austere dignified in style as they are pregnant with practical wisdom. The same versatility is evident in trifles.

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